

EFFECTIVE ACTIVE LEARNING – PEDAGOGY FOR EVIDENCE-BASED FLIPPED CLASSROOM

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Abstract

This paper shares an evidence-based pedagogic model for implementing a highly effective flipped classroom approach. The approach presented both maximizes an active learning approach and the learning affordances of info-communication technologies. It firstly explains what a flipped classroom is, its key pedagogic features and potential learning benefits in terms of the student learning experience and outcomes. Secondly, it highlights the importance of designing and facilitating student learning experiences based on instructional methods that, from extensive research, suggest the most positive effects on attainment, based on a measurement parameter known as ‘Effect Size’. Examples of high effect size instructional strategies in the context of this work are outlined, as well as the creative blending of particular methods and e-tools, which can result in especially high impact learning experiences and attainment opportunities for students. The pedagogic approach also incorporates ‘Core Principles of Learning’ as fundamental design heuristics in the construction of instructional strategies, and strongly emphasizes that good pedagogy must come before technology in learning design. Technology will not make a poorly designed lesson an engaging and effective one; however, it can significantly enhance aspects of the learning process in the case of well-designed lessons. This is essential in the case of the flipped classroom as the important overall design consideration is how best to maximize the learning affordances of both online and face-to-face modes of instruction. Thirdly, there is a particular focus on creating an overall active learning environment to facilitate high levels of student engagement and two-way feedback relating to formative assessment, which has a particularly high effect size for enhancing student attainment. Quality feedback makes both student learning and faculty thinking visible, thus enabling accurate assessment of present performance levels, identification of learning gaps, and planning effective strategies to meet desired goals. The final section of the paper summarizes and illustrates the full pedagogic framework and how it can be systematically employed in designing and facilitating highly effective flipped classroom lessons.

Keywords: *Flipped classroom, evidence-based teaching, formative assessment, ICT Tools*

Active Learning and Flipped Classroom

Active learning is generally defined as any instructional method that engages students in the learning process. In short, active learning requires students to do meaningful learning activities and think about what they are doing (e.g. Bonwell & Eison, 1991). There are many forms of active learning strategies, and evidence from the literature shows that they can be effective in improving student learning compared to traditional lecture (e.g. Prince, 2004). The latest form of active learning that had caught widespread attention is flipped classroom. The flipped classroom is essentially a blended learning format for organizing the student learning experience utilizing the potential benefits of blended learning. While there are many definitions of blended learning, Garisson & Vaughan (2008) capture the key elements nicely when they assert it

...is the thoughtful fusion of face-to-face and online learning experience...optimally integrated such that the strengths and weakness of each are blended into a unique learning experience congruent with the context and intended educational purpose.

...combines the properties and possibilities of both to go beyond the capabilities of each separately. (p.6)

The basic approach in flipped classroom is that students are given an online learning experience before coming to class, often through a recorded lecture and related reading and activities (previous done through the face-to-face class lecture), which is to help them acquire the key underpinning knowledge relating to a topic area before the face-to-face session. This approach is to free up class time to apply the content knowledge thoughtfully in more real-world active learning application. Various authors had mentioned the potential benefits of flipped classroom (e.g. Fulton, 2012; Herreid & Schiller, 2013) which include:

- students being able to learn more at their own pace
- doing “homework” in class gives teachers better insight into student difficulties

- teachers can more easily customize and update the curriculum to meet students learning needs as they arise
- classroom time can be used more effectively and creatively
- students who miss class can watch the lectures in their own time
- students are more actively involved in the learning process
- a greater positive impact on attainment and the learning experience than the traditional mode (based on self-reporting)

At present, research relating to the effectiveness of the flip format is more descriptive rather than empirically validated (e.g. Waldrop & Bowden, 2015). Similarly, Murray, Koziniec & McGill (2015) noted that although flipped classroom has received a lot of publicity, there has been little formal evaluation of its impact on student satisfaction or performance. As will be introduced later, an evidence-based pedagogical approach offers greater effectiveness in evaluating the flipped classroom in terms of its potential for enhancing student learning experiences and attainment opportunities.

Evidence-based Approach to Teaching and Learning

Slavin (2008) argued that “throughout the history of education, the adoption of instructional programs and practices has been driven more by ideology, faddism, politics, and marketing than by evidence.” Certainly for many decades, it seemed, as Sallis & Hingley (1991) commented, “Education is a creature of fashion.” As a consequence, many teachers consider that effective teaching is such a common-sense endeavor that comes naturally (Halpern & Hakel, 2003). However, many typical practices of teachers, such as long heavy content lectures, do not concur with what is known about human learning (Saville, 2010). One therefore has to be cognizant of the need to continually improve our teaching to maximize student learning. Groccia and Buskit (2011) for example, noted that “...as teachers, it is always *necessary* (italics in original) to improve.”

An evidence-based approach to teaching and learning refers to the pedagogical knowledge, method use and principles of learning that have shown, through extensive research, to promote better learning (Saville, 2010; Dunn et al, 2013). This is crucial to maximize student learning opportunities and for educators to have evidence about their learning and performance in order to support them to achieve better quality educational outcomes. To this end, the process of evidence gathering to inform teaching and learning must be an explicit and accountable one, which is equitable, representative, valid, and reliable (Bruniges, 2005).

Of particular significance in this area is the work of Hattie (e.g. 2009; 2012), which was an educational landmark in the movement away from more ideological-based paradigms towards evidence-based practice in teaching. Hattie synthesized over 800 meta-analyses of

the influences on learning and most significantly, he was interested not just in what factors impacted learning, but the extent of their impact - referred to as *Effect-Size*. Effect size is a way to measure the effectiveness of a particular intervention to ascertain a measure of both the *improvement* (gain) in learner achievement for a group of learners and the *variation* of learner performances expressed on a standardised scale. By taking into account both *improvement* and *variation* it provides information to which interventions are worth having.

Hattie firstly identified the typical effect sizes of schooling without specific interventions, for example, what gains in attainment are we likely to expect over a one-year academic cycle? Typically, for students moving from one year to the next, the average effect size across all students is 0.40. Hence, for Hattie, effect sizes above 0.4 are of particular interest. As a baseline an effect size of 1.0 is massive and is typically associated with:

- Advancing the learner’s achievement by one year
- Improving the rate of learning by 50%
- A two grade leap in GCSE grades

Table 1 shows examples of effect sizes in learner attainment from Hattie’s meta-analysis which featured some high impact methods on student attainment, as demonstrated by their effect size.

Table 1. Examples of effect sizes (Hattie, 2009)

Influence	Mean Effect Size
Feedback Students getting feedback on their work from the teacher, their peers or some other sources. Note: some feedback has more effect size than others. For example, peer assessment is 0.63 and self-assessment is 0.54	0.73
Meta-cognitive strategies Students can systematically think about (plan, monitor and evaluate) their own thinking and affective processes (e.g. beliefs, emotions, dispositions) to develop effective learning to learn capability and self-regulation	0.69
Challenging goals Students having a clear frame on, and see purpose in, what they are learning, as well as experience realistic challenge in meeting goal expectations	0.56
Advanced organizers Giving students an overview (in an appropriate format and level of understanding) of what is to be learned in advance of the lesson, to help make meaningful connections between their prior knowledge and the new material to be presented	0.41

However, as Hattie notes, it is important to balance effect size with the level of difficulty of interventions. For example, providing ‘advance organizers’ (summaries in advance of the teaching) have an effect size of 0.41, which is pretty average, but they only take

up a few minutes at the beginning of the lesson, and potentially offer the equivalent of moving up a year in terms of a student's achievement. He goes on to make relative comparisons of intervention use, which enables us to go beyond identifying the effect sizes for particular innovations (deliberative intervention involving strategy/method use for a group of students), and ascertain whether the effects of a particular innovation were better for students than what they would achieve if they had received alternative innovations.

Of particular significance is the fact that it is not just the effect size of one intervention that is important, but how a number of effective methods can be strategically and creatively combined to produce powerful instructional strategies that significantly impact student attainment. As Hattie (2009) pointed out:

...some effect sizes are 'Russian dolls' containing more than one strategy. For example, 'Feedback' requires that the student has been given a goal, and completed an activity for which the feedback is to be given; 'whole-class interactive teaching' is a strategy that includes 'advance organizers' and feedback and reviews. (p.62)

Figure 1. Russian dolls (source: www.kzero.co.uk)

Core Principles of Learning

From an evidence-based perspective, it is not just the methods that work best, but also the underlying core principles of learning that facilitate the learning process (e.g. Ambrose, Bridges, DiPietro, Lovett and Norman, 2010; Willingham, 2009). For example, Sale (2015) offers the following 10 Core principles of Learning as key guiding heuristics from which teaching professionals can plan learning experiences and teach more effectively:

1. Motivational strategies are incorporated into the design of learning experiences
2. Learning goals, objectives and proficiency expectations are clearly visible to learners
3. Learners prior knowledge is activated and connected to new learning
4. Content is organized around key concepts and principles that are fundamental to understanding the structure of a subject
5. Good thinking promotes the building of understanding

6. Instructional methods and presentation mediums engage the range of human of senses
7. Learning design takes into account the working of memory systems
8. The development of expertise requires deliberate practice
9. A psychological climate is created which is both success-orientated and fun
10. Assessment practices are integrated into the learning design to promote desired learning outcomes and provide quality feedback

The 10 Core Principles of Learning are not exhaustive or summative as new knowledge and insights will continually enhance our understanding of human learning and the implications for how we teach. However, as Willingham (2009) rightly noted:

Principles of physics do not prescribe for a civil engineer exactly how to build a bridge, but they do let him predict how it is likely to perform if he builds it. Similarly, cognitive scientific principles do not prescribe how to teach, but they can help you predict how much your students are likely to learn. If you follow these principles, you maximize the chances that your students will flourish. (p.165)

Furthermore, just as combining high effect methods can have a powerful overall impact on learner attainment, as captured in Hattie's (2009) analogy of 'Russian Dolls', the same applies to the thoughtful and creative application of core principles of learning. As Stigler & Hiebert (1999) highlighted:

Teaching is a *system*. It is not a loose mixture of individual features thrown together by the teacher. It works more like a machine, with the parts operating together and reinforcing one another, driving the vehicle forward. (p.75)

Assessment for Learning (Formative Assessment)

As shown in Table 1, feedback given in the form of formative assessment is an important intervention with high effect size (0.73). Formative assessment is a planned process by which assessment-elicited evidence of students' status is used by teachers to adjust their ongoing instructional procedures or by students to adjust their current learning tactics (Popham, 2011). As noted by Marzano (2009):

In terms of providing teachers with feedback, the focus must always be on student learning and the perspective must always be that the instructional strategies are a means to an end.

The evidence that formative assessment is a powerful lever for improving outcomes for learners has been steadily accumulating over the last quarter of a century. Over that time, at least 15 substantial reviews of research, synthesizing several thousand research studies, have documented the impact of classroom assessment practices on students. The general finding is that across a range of different school subjects, in different countries, and for learners of different ages, the use of formative assessment appears to be associated

with considerable improvements in the rate of learning (Leahy and Wiliam, 2012).

Black et al (2003) noted that the concept of ‘feedback’ is central to the operation of any system that has to adapt to manage change, of which formative assessment is one. These authors listed four key components required for effective feedback:

- Data on the actual level of some measurable attribute
- Data on the desirable level of that attribute
- A mechanism for comparing the two levels and assessing the gap between them
- A mechanism by which the information can be used to alter the gap

Affordances in Info-Communication Technologies

The flipped classroom is fundamentally about good pedagogic design, and that needs to be evidence-based in terms of the methods that work best and what we know about how humans learn – the core principles of learning. However, in the context of this paper, info-communication technologies (ICT) are seen as offering key affordances in terms of enhancing effectiveness and efficiency in the learning process. ICT in this context refers to the freely available Web 2.0 Tools as well as specialized computer simulation and modelling softwares for use in teaching and in enhancing student learning. Reddi (2007) noted that when a decision is taken to use ICTs for educational purposes, we must be able to define and describe for what purpose the content will be used and also be very clear as to what delivery system we are going to use. Such a decision should not be based on the technologies but on the conditions and contexts in which we seek to use the ICTs; from simple access to modules or to enhance specific aspects of the learning process. Although the above-mentioned core principles of learning did not make explicit references to ICTs, their use is particularly noticeable in Principle No.10 for facilitating the feedback process. In practice, ICT tools are useful in supporting all core principles of learning. For example, Principle No.3 via web site links to earlier topics; and Principle No.9 by including in the learning process elements of play. ICT tools can also be used to promote good thinking (Principle No.5) but as noted by Sale (2014), we need to be clear from a pedagogical point of view about the types of thinking that we are trying to promote and provide practice in, as technologies themselves do not ensure good thinking.

Flipped Classroom: An Evidence-based Pedagogy

An example of the pedagogical model, which combines the most effective methods, principles of learning and the affordances of ICT, is shown in Figure 2. Student learning starts with learning of disciplinary knowledge outside of classroom. This is usually a video recording of a PowerPoint-based lecture created using Camtasia or YouTube videos uploaded by professional organizations. This is followed by a self-evaluation exercise (usually multiple choice questions or true/false

questions, created for example using Socrative or Kahoot) for students to monitor his/her understanding of the topic concerned. Feedback is formative, whereby brief explanation for all answers (right or wrong) are provided. Evidence of students learning can be discerned from the result captured. When in class, the lecturer will engage students firstly by pointing to an advanced organizer that described the day’s lessons and how the topics are tied into the overall module learning aims. The learning outcomes for the day are then explained. Depending on the difficulty of the topic concerned, the lecturer may use the concept checkpoint to further ascertain students’ understanding before proceeding. The lecturer then introduces various class activities, based on the learning context requirements, using videos, short case studies, news clippings, simulations, etc so that students get to practice thinking and deliberate practice in applying the concepts learned. Again, depending on the difficulty of the topics, the lecturer may introduce additional concept checkpoints, usually by asking relevant probing questions. The lecturer can conclude the day’s lesson with a summary of concepts covered, and where necessary, initiate another round of concept checking.

Figure 2. Example of an Evidence-based Flipped Classroom Format

This process may be repeated a number of times to facilitate the necessary practice and reinforcement for memory to build up of key competencies. Subsequent lessons will build on the topics covered earlier, and further concept checkpoints may be used as needed to ensure students are able to integrate earlier learning into the current context.

Classroom discussions may require students to provide answers in class, using platforms such as Google Doc, or Padlet (which is a form of digital Post-It notes). For example, students may be given a topic and are asked to discuss in groups and present a jointly-reasoned answer in Google Doc. Individual students

may also be asked to provide input using Padlet. These student responses are projected onto the screen and allow the lecturer to quickly ascertain if students understand all the key concepts taught up to that point. Responses from groups that consistently missed out on an item may point to significant gaps and misconceptions relating to particular concepts in a topic.

To better prepare students for a graded-assessment, such as a written assignment, a mock test is administered, and the report submitted by students are marked with focused annotations to provide task- and process-specific feedback. Classroom discussion focuses on key areas of improvement so that gaps in knowledge and thinking can be made visible and collaboratively addressed. Another effective and efficient method to help students learn important process assessment skills is via peer marking using a given set of rubrics. Students are taught how to mark a set of model answers. It is worthy to note that some of the responses in the model answers were made to be deliberately less-than-satisfactory, challenging them to identify the shortcomings in the answers, and to offer ways to improve these answers. The rubrics thus serve to inform students of our expectations. For more challenging topics, additional self-learning activities are provided for students practice before embarking on the graded-assessment (summative).

Evaluating a Flipped Classroom

In evaluating the student learning experience of the flipped classroom, it is important to recognize that some areas are generic to the context of learning, e.g. the learning space, resource access and technical design and functionality. Hence, in conducting evaluation, such features may need to be ascertained and taken into consideration, as well as specific pedagogic focal areas.

In this work, we used an evidence-based approach as the guiding heuristics for evaluating the instructional design and teaching practices, as well as the students learning experiences. For the latter, the aim is to unpack the components of the experience and identify which features have most significantly impacted student learning (e.g. positively, negatively or other), and on what basis. To assist this process, we have enlisted the participation (voluntarily) of at least two students per class as “co-participants” (Lincoln, 1990) in the research process. They provide regular feedback on their learning, and that of classmates (where possible) through focus group interviews and questionnaires. This enables ongoing appraisal of the instructional strategy, evidence-based diagnosis of student learning, both in terms of attainment and experience. In this way, modifications and new components can be introduced with a high predictive capability of being effective and efficient in the learning stakes.

Conclusions

The challenge of designing and facilitating the student learning experience from an evidence-based teaching approach using the flipped classroom format was an exciting one. Certainly we feel that the approach shared in this paper is the most logical theory-based instructional model to underpin our teaching using the flip classroom format. This is crucial, as Black and Wiliam (1998) summarize:

Teachers will not take up attractive sounding ideas, albeit based on extensive research, if these are presented as general principles which leave entirely to them the task of translating them into everyday practice – their classroom lives are too busy and too fragile for this to be possible for all but an outstanding few. What they need is a variety of living examples of implementation, by teachers with whom they can identify and from whom they can both derive connection and confidence that they can do better, and see concrete examples of what doing better means in practice.

Similarly, Dziuban, Hartman & Moskal (2004) point out:

Maximizing success in a blended learning initiative requires a planned and well supported approach that includes a theory-based instructional model, high quality faculty development, course development assistance, [and] learner support. (p.3)

This approach is now being piloted with the Diploma in Chemical Engineering in Singapore Polytechnic, and detailed work is covered elsewhere by Cheah (2016). Our future goal is to improve the capability of maximizing the blend of high effect size teaching methods and the affordances of the flip format to create highly effective, efficient and creative learning experiences for the students we teach. This we feel is a real merging of the science, art and craft of teaching (Eisner, 1995).

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